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D9.1 First Interim report on Transnational Access 2

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
TA	Transnational Access
RIL	Research Infrastructure Leader
CA	Contract Agreement
BA	Bilateral Agreement

Executive summary

This document aims to present an overview of the Transnational Access (TA) activities conducted in Work Package 9 (WP9) TA2 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care as part of the VITALISE project. This first interim report encompasses four research infrastructures that participated in the context of this work package, presenting information for both completed TA activities and also for the upcoming TA activities scheduled for the project's final phase.

In particular, the report includes comprehensive information for each of the participating research infrastructures. For completed TA activities, it provides a summary of every research project, the activities performed, the outcomes achieved, and any notable findings or advancements made. In addition, the report for the completed TA activities includes also some information regarding the effort and hours spent from the several professionals of the LL personnel for supporting the execution of each TA activity, both in person and remotely, as well as a summary of the researchers' TA evaluation and potential opportunities for future collaboration and common publications. This information showcases the value and impact of the TA program on the overall project objectives. Additionally, the document outlines the upcoming TA activities that are going to be carried out during the project's final phase. It includes details such as the planned research objectives, anticipated benefits, and expected outcomes. These planned TA activities represent the project's ongoing commitment to exploring new avenues of research and maximizing the potential of Living Lab infrastructures.

As it is the first interim report, this document offers a snapshot of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP9's TA2. It signifies the project's progress towards fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of transitional care. This report serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, providing insights into the project's TA outcomes and setting the stage for the comprehensive final report due in Month 36.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP9

Work Package 9 (WP9) is focused on the centralized and coordinated design and implementation of Transnational Access for Infrastructures related with the domain of transitional care. The term "Transnational Access" (TA) refers to the usage of VITALISE infrastructures by researchers located in countries other than where the accessed infrastructure is located.

WP9 encompasses four research infrastructures: 1) AUTH Health care transition Living Lab, 2) INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room, 3) Thomas More experience lab and 4) UPM-LifeSTech- The Smart House Living Lab.

The support offered during TA visits includes, but is not limited to, logistics management, provision of working space, scientific support by Living Lab researchers for stakeholder management, assistance in preparing and submitting ethical applications, conducting experiments, and technical support for maintenance or resolving technology issues, if necessary.

The TA procedure and manual is handled in WP11 NA4 - Calls for ideas and proposals, experiment selection. Efforts for outreach to new users are described in WP13, utilizing the project website and existing communication channels of ENoLL, EIT Health LL, and Forum LLSA. Capacity-building activities in WP4 and the calls in WP11 facilitate outreach and selection of approved proposals. The financial support for travel and accommodation provided to researchers is expected to increase transnational access to the infrastructures.

1.2 Purpose of the document

The purpose of the D9.1 "First Interim Report on Transnational Access 2" is to summarize the activities conducted under the VITALISE project's Work Package 9 TA2 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care. The report includes both completed and upcoming transnational access activities across four research infrastructures. It details the research conducted, the outcomes, significant findings and the researchers' evaluation for completed activities, while outlining planned objectives, benefits, and expected results for upcoming activities. This interim report serves as an essential resource for stakeholders, providing insights into the project's progress and laying the groundwork for the final report, offering preliminary insights that will be further developed and expanded upon in the D9.2 document, the "Final Report on Transnational Access 2" setting the stage for the final report (D9.2, due on month 36, March 2024).

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1 (Introduction)** provides a description of Work Package 9 (WP9), outlines the purpose of the document, and presents the structure of the report.
- **Section 2 (Finalized Transnational Access Projects)** provides details for each Transnational Access (TA) project, evaluation from researchers, and some information about the number of hours spent by the Living Lab personnel.
- **Section 3 (Planning of Upcoming TA Projects)** offers updates on overall planning. For each Living Lab infrastructure, it presents data for each planned TA, such as the project name, planned TA period, Consortium Agreement (CA) signed and uploaded by the applicants, CA signed by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), CA sent and signed by the applicants, signing of the Bilateral Agreement (BA, if applicable), initial questionnaires, and visits performed.
- **Section 4 (Conclusion)** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2 Finalized Transnational Access projects

This section presents one by one the TA projects that have been performed in each of the WP9 Living Lab infrastructures so far.

2.1 AUTH Health care transition Living Lab

At this point, one study has already been completed in AUTH Health care transition Living Lab, named “Gold Health Care” project (ID9) which is described in this section. In total, there are two more accepted projects that will be conducted in the upcoming months, “Hestia – the care support platform unlocking healthy ageing and caring” (ID21) and “Digital Support for Cancer Survivors: Opportunities for Software, Agents, and Robotics Intervention” (ID35). More information on these upcoming studies conducted in AUTH Health care transition Living Lab is included in the next section.

2.1.1 Gold Health Care project (ID9)

2.1.1.1 Project summary

The main purpose of the “Gold Health Care” project is to implement innovative approaches to healthcare tailored to vulnerable groups of older adults for better healthcare and aging. The project consists of three main stages that build upon each other: a. preliminary context analysis, assessment of barriers and stakeholder analysis; b. development of tailored healthcare interventions; implementation, c. evaluation and dissemination. The Gold Health Care project aims to offer innovative and holistic approaches to care, providing five (5) services: health care for elderly vulnerable groups, community health education including e-health, capacity building of health professionals and academic staff, and employment of nursing students). All the aforementioned services are provided in one shot and maximizing the effectiveness of interventions among vulnerable groups of older adults in the local population. The project envisages to create a wide local knowledge framework, detailing health care barriers, facilitators and needs among vulnerable groups of older people through working in close collaboration with them, then use the findings to generate evidence-based interventions and policies.

Within this context, in AUTH infrastructures the visiting research team aimed to conduct a first mapping and evaluation of the barriers, challenges, shortcomings but, also, the benefits of health care interventions targeting vulnerable groups of older people.

For the purposes of this TA, four researchers, Fatjona Kamberi (lead applicant), Glodiana Sinanaj, Brunilda Subashi and Jerina Jaho from the University of Vlora "Ismail Qemali" visited AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab in Thessaloniki, Greece. The visiting period for the four researchers was the week from the 20th till the 24th of February 2023. During this period, they were introduced to various technologies and resources available in the lab and they had the opportunity to conduct two co-creation sessions, one with health care professionals and one with older adults. Before the conduction of the co-creation sessions, the VITALISE research team along with the visiting researchers discussed the details of the sessions, how and where they will be held, and also information about the participants' profile. Moreover, they created a list of indicative questions for guiding the semi-structured interview during the sessions, and also, highlighted some points regarding the ethical framework and the data management.

The co-creation sessions were facilitated by the lab's research personnel and aimed to gather input from healthcare professionals and patients on the challenges and opportunities of transitional care. Through these sessions, the researchers were able to gain valuable insights and perspectives from those directly involved in the healthcare system.

In particular, the first co-creation session was composed of seven healthcare professionals, including specialists in cardiology, surgery, psychology, and general medicine, aged between 20-45 and having 2-25 years of clinical practice. This session was held in the settings of the “Hippokratation” General Hospital of Thessaloniki in the English language. A semi-structured interview guide was used, including open key questions, introductory questions, and transition questions, focusing on

difficulties in discharge and transfer processes for older patients with complex care needs, patients' perceptions of discharge and transfer, resources required for optimal transfers, and how these difficulties are alleviated. In general, it was highlighted by the participants a lack of communication among key healthcare actors, which makes difficult for them to discharge and transfer older people with complicated needs. Heart failure, stroke, and neurological disorders were the most often mentioned chronic care diseases requiring transitional care and the severity of the problem was one of the most often mentioned grounds for moving patients from the hospital to transitional care. The patients' perceptions of discharge and transitions were primarily attributed to their knowledge of the recommended treatment regimens.

The second co-creation session consisted of 10 members of the AUTH LL community, aged between 65-90, and it was conducted in AUTH living environment simulation in the Greek language, with the support of the VITALISE research team. For this session, a combination of validated standardized questionnaires and a list of guiding questions was used, in relation to chronic care and quality of life. In total, almost all the participants expressed an overall good health and mental status, good quality of life and, also, a good level in operating daily activities, walking and taking care of themselves. However, there were some participants who expressed being slightly anxious or depressed during the past period.

During the last days of the visit, the AUTH LL research team along with the visiting researchers discussed the analysis strategy and next steps for common publication. A qualitative analysis of both the co-creation sessions is planned to take place, based on the participants' answers and remarks. For this purpose, the AUTH LL personnel have already carried out a transcription of the two co-creation sessions held in AUTH LL infrastructures.

For supporting the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. In particular, apart from the LL manager who was also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), two Ethics & Security Managers were involved, also two Administrative & Financial Managers, one technical expert, one psychologist and some other supportive LL personnel (4 more people). In total, approximately 127 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of "Gold Health Care" project in AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab, both in person and remotely, which is translated to around 14 person days.

The final report of this TA is included in the Annex 1 – Report on TA ID9.

2.1.1.2 TA Evaluation

In the evaluation questionnaire, all the visiting researchers declared that the output of TA was much better than expected, even though they had very high expectations before the beginning of their study. In advance, they had mainly indicated that through this TA, they would like to gain knowledge and expertise regarding LL infrastructures, fostering that way their skills in research implementation and transferring this knowledge to their country. Regarding the Fast Track Training Program, all the researchers pointed out that it was much better than expected and that all the training blocks were of very high quality and usefulness. They highlighted that it was very practical for them and facilitated them to make the connection of the theory with some more practical aspects of Living Labs. Most of the Living Lab services provided during TA (understand end-users needs and problems, methodological support and guidance, selection/recruitment of test persons, expertise/support with end-users, physical infrastructure) were rated very high in terms of quality. Key strengths of AUTH LL comprised the multidisciplinary research team and very good organization of the infrastructure which facilitate their access for conducting their study. All within VITALISE developed products (Data tool, Panel management tool, VITALISE website, and VITALISE wiki page) were rated high or very high in terms of usefulness and user friendliness by most of the visiting researchers, apart from Data tool, Panel management tool and VITALISE website, which were lower rated by one of the researchers. Lastly, all the researchers declared that they consider very probable to need these services and in their future work. To conclude, the transnational access of the four visiting researchers from the University of Vlore "Ismail Qemali" paved the way for a new collaboration between the two universities aiming, also, at a joint publication in the near future. These activities ensure the sustainability of Living Labs' services; thus, this TA is considered a great success.

2.2 INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room

At this point, a first study is currently running, finalizing by the end of July 2023, with the posterior final reporting (ID 13), which focus is Investigating Kinematic Outputs in Immersive 3D, VR Environments. The second accepted project addresses research focused on Utilizing Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality for Early Dementia Detection, which TA is planned for October-November 2023 (ID42) and it is included in the next section.

2.2.1 VirtuaLearn - Neural aspects of motor learning in a fully immersive VR environment (ID13)

2.2.1.1 Project summary

Researchers: Luka Slozar (Lead Applicant), Uros Marusic, Manca Peskar (Science and Research Centre Koper, Institute for Kinesiology Research) (note: initially the Agreement for Transnational Access signed included a fourth researcher, Aleksandar Miladinovic).

Presented Study: This project is focused on understanding the mechanisms involved in learning movement kinematic output in an immersive 3D virtual reality (VR) environment. The goal is to advance the ecological validity of research in motor control by using immersive technologies like Head-Mounted Displays (HMDs) and Cave Automatic Virtual Environments (CAVE). The Fitts Law Model, a well-established predictive model of motor learning, will be translated from 2D to a fully immersive 3D VR setting. The project further aims to harness the potential of technologies like mobile brain/body imaging (MoBI) and telemedicine to study and facilitate the rehabilitation process. Ultimately, the project aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge in the intersection of motor learning, neurophysiology, and VR, and to potentially enhance rehabilitation techniques using immersive technologies.

Accepted Under Conditions: Researchers required having from the Living Lab a fully dedicated software developer with experience with Unity to work full-time on the project and develop the Fitts Law Model, but this was not feasible. Without a full-time software developer on your team, it was not feasible to create the Fitts' Law program from scratch as initially planned. Due to this limitation, changes were made to the research plans. Thus, the interaction took a different, albeit equally beneficial, form. Instead, Gradior Multisensorial app developed by INTRAS & IDES S.L. was an instrumental case study for the research team. This Virtual Reality (VR) tool applies a snoezelen multisensory stimulation approach, aiming to enhance emotional well-being and behavioral regulation.

The researchers were provided with a license for testing, and several meetings were held to discuss the practical implementation of the tool and the effects previously observed in studies. A workshop was also held to introduce the scientific basis of the VR multisensory approach, a demo session and further discussion.

The information and experience exchange proved valuable as it served as a foundation for the team's own prototype. Building on these insights, the research team is currently developing a study that is expected to commence towards the end of the year. The lessons learned from this process will likely play a significant role in shaping the design and implementation of this upcoming study.

In brief, final refined focus was on gaining experience with the VR environments and tasks used in the LL, building upon the research team new study protocol using the knowledge acquired from that experience.

For supporting the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. Apart from the LL manager who was also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), one technical manager, one Psychologist, two software developers (the second as a substitute), one Administrative & Financial Manager, and one technical expert were involved.

In total, approximately 106 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of this TA in the INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room infrastructure, fully remotely, which is translated to around 13 person days.

The final report of this TA is not included in the appendix since it is still pending. It will be included in the next deliverable.

2.2.1.2 TA evaluation

Making a summarized analysis of the questionnaires provided by the researchers, some of the researchers remained neutral in stating their expectations, but still expected to gain new collaboration options, new knowledge for their team, expanded professional network, future collaboration and knowledge related to VR environments. Within the objectives they set out to achieve, in the follow-up questionnaire of the first week we can see that they already come into contact with them through familiarisation with VR environments and networking, rating the AT with a high score. From the second week onwards they start to develop the research protocol, during the following weeks they report acquiring more valuable knowledge that they can incorporate into their research. The final report and the last questionnaire are being completed, nevertheless, from the questionnaires delivered, all the assessments made were rated very highly. In conclusion, the remote access of the three visiting researchers was a successful opportunity of learning and generating ideas for new developments and research related to VR environments.

2.3 Thomas More experience lab

None of the TA projects using the THOMAS MORE Experience lab infrastructure has started at this point. The first study (ID 36) is expected for the end of August 2023. A second project is planned in January 2024. More information on these upcoming studies conducted in the THOMAS MORE Experience lab is included in the next section.

2.4 UPM-LifeSTech- LifeSpace Living Lab

None of the TA projects using the LifeSpace Living Lab infrastructure has started at this point. The first study (ID 93) is expected to start in October 2023. More information on these upcoming studies conducted in the LifeSpace Living Lab is included in the next section.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

3 Planning of upcoming TA projects

Due to the fact that this document is an interim report and not all the TAs have been finalized yet, this section provides an overview and a short description of the upcoming TA projects that will be performed in the WP9 Living Lab infrastructures.

3.1 Overall planning updates

Below we present an infographic with information about the WP9 TA to Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care research studies. The infographic includes aggregated information from the three (3) VITALISE Open calls, taking into account both completed and upcoming projects.

Figure 1 Infographic for the TA to Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care research studies

In the initial planning we have targeted 6 external researchers to each Living Lab Infrastructure. As the transitional care thematic included 4 Research Infrastructures, we were targeting for a total of 24 researchers. The 28 applicants exceeded the initial expectations, not counting the applications that were considered non-feasible. We have also achieved a perfect gender balance (50%-50%) and a good distribution of working countries for the applicants. The final headcount of the visiting researchers is a bit smaller as one researcher decided not to participate but that did not affect the quality of the study. All the WP9 TA researchers are coming from the academia, which is a limitation for our RIs, however it is considered normal as the transitional care is a clinical domain that many companies find difficulties to address.

3.2 AUTH Health care transition Living Lab

Here we include a table that presents the current status of each upcoming TA project in AUTH Health care transition Living Lab.

Table 1 Current status of each of each upcoming TA project in AUTH Health care transition Living Lab

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENOLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
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ID21	SEP-OCT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID35	SEP-OCT	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

ID21 Theofanis Fotis (Lead applicant) & Lydia Koumarela, University of Brighton, Tendertec.

The scope of this project named “Hestia – the care support platform unlocking healthy ageing and caring” is to explore informal caregivers’ experiences with Hestia’s Care Assistant Platform and sensors in managing better the burden of care as a part of the pilot. It is expected that Hestia’s insights will shine a light on the impact unpaid care has on informal caregivers and hopefully to influence policy. Hestia is a privacy-preserving care support platform, with no wearables and no cameras, that captures missed hazards and early exacerbation symptoms.

More specifically, Tendertec’s sensors are fitted inside living spaces and collect data about movements. The aim is to conduct a real-life testing of the effectiveness of Hestia’s insights in giving carers the confidence they need to manage caring duties and have a life outside caring without worry, guilt, and stress. Hestia insights aims to provide carers with reassurance their loved one is ok and confidence to make preventive care decisions to avoid exacerbations. As part of this trial, the Hestia Care Assistant App will support unpaid carers to have more time for themselves on prevention to by:

- Allowing them to connect and check-in with their loved one anytime and anywhere to ensure they do not miss a thing even when they are not at home.
- Alerting them of missed incidents, fall-risk behaviours, changes in daily living activity (e.g., sleeping, activity levels, night wandering, eating & drinking) and early symptoms of disease exacerbation (e.g., abnormal body temperature) to prevent small issues from escalating into bigger problems.
- Enabling them to reconstruct and review any incident (e.g., fall or seizure) to understand not just when it happened, but also why and how it happened - they key to prevention.

The steps that will be followed for this is the following: firstly conduct some semi-structured interviews, like open discussions, with the older adults and their carers, then install the devices at the older adults’ homes and give access and explain the Hestia Care Assistant App to the carers, and afterwards collect quantitative and qualitative feedback regarding the usability and feasibility of the device and proof of value. Within this context, will be also explored the transcultural differences between UK/ Greece, as well as the effect of infrastructure differences regarding the installation and use of the tested technologies.

ID35 Alessio Antonini (Lead applicant) & Iman Naja, Open University-United Kingdom.

The current study, named “Digital Support for Cancer Survivors: Opportunities for Software, Agents, and Robotics Intervention” aims to validate the design of the AI model for ‘intelligent companions developed in the UK within the different Greek context, which would be capable of life-long support by alleviating the burden of self-management in a life-long setting, with the broader aim to support the vision of self-driven healthcare.

This entails implementing, expanding, and evolving solutions for preventions and interventions, both software related and those involving autonomous robotics agents. In this context, a second aim is to scope the requirements for autonomous robotics agents that would be involved in at-home care to support self-management and independent living for cancer survivors.

According to previous literature, digital health management has proven beneficial during trials, but the resulting technologies have shown low acceptance and uptake. One of the objectives of this project is to study the design flaws of such technologies that lead to their low acceptance and uptake,

taking into consideration the unmet needs of patients and survivors as well as the socio-cultural aspects of the deployment of such technologies.

During the visiting period in the AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab the aim is to gain insights from the participants (cancer patients and survivors, health care professionals and informal caregivers) through co-creation workshops, expert consultations, and advisory services. These will include focus groups, surveys, and semi-structured, as well as co-producing artifacts. The second step will be thematic analysis of the acquired data.

3.3 INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room

Here we include a table that presents the current status of each upcoming TA project in INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room.

Table 2 Current status of each upcoming TA project in INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID42	OCT-NOV	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO

ID42 Fátima Gonzalez Palau, Gonzalez Palau Center for Psychotherapy, Neuropsychology and Neurorehabilitation, Argentina.

IDENTIA - Development of a screening system based on Virtual Reality technologies for the identification of preclinical phases of dementia applying machine learning and deep learning techniques.

The IDENTIA project addresses the global urgency of early dementia detection using AI and VR technologies. Through predictive models using cognitive indicators, the project aims to diagnose dementia at the subclinical stage, leveraging neuropsychological assessments in a virtual environment. This novel method presents a cost-effective, non-invasive, and highly sensitive approach to early detection, promising a significant improvement in patient quality of life.

Access to the INTRAS Living Lab will also allow the IDENTIA project to benefit from the lab's therapeutic VR research and extensive experience in geriatric and palliative care services. The lab, equipped with advanced IT software and devices for training, rehabilitation, and daily living assistance, is an ideal setting for fostering the project's digital cognitive assessments, facilitating a pre-validation of the research premises in real living and working environments, in the course of the project committed to developing more effective early detection methods.

This will be invaluable in optimizing the project's strategies, for later carrying out experimental studies involving a sample of 200 older adults, and ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of early dementia detection methods, moving us closer towards a more sustainable and responsive healthcare system in the face of demographic challenges.

3.4 Thomas More experience lab

Here we include a table that presents the current status of each upcoming TA project in Thomas More experience lab.

Table 3 Current status of each upcoming TA project in Thomas More experience lab

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by EnoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID 36	AUG23	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO
ID 61	JAN 24	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO

ID 36 Theodor-Radu Grumeza, Dorin Cazan, Richard Baczur, Daniel Miron, West University of Timisoara, Romania.

This study is named ChatterGlove – A healthcare appliance for speech/hearing impaired individuals. Individuals with a speech or hearing impairment can have difficulties to communicate effectively. These impairments can have an impact on their interactions with others, educational opportunities, employment prospects, feelings of isolation and exclusion, and overall quality of life. However, with the implementation of inclusive practices, assistive innovative technologies, and supportive workplace environments, these barriers can be overcome.

One example of such a technological innovation is the ChatterGlove, an exoskeleton that aims to translate sign language into spoken or written text. The core aim of the ChatterGlove is to offer a healthcare appliance that will help speech or hearing-impaired individuals to communicate in a simple manner by using a 3D printed exoskeleton glove, which by means of electronic modules aims to translate hand signals and gestures into written text and speech.

The current study aims to investigate user experience and user acceptance of the ChatterGlove prototype, an exoskeleton prototype that intends to translate sign language into spoken or written text.

In the first part of the study, we focus on user experience and user acceptance of individuals with speech/hearing difficulties. During the second part of the study, which comprises two co-creation sessions, the goal is to collect feedback about the potential use of the ChatterGlove from technical and (para)medical experts. Feedback collected during both parts of the study will be used to make improvements in the design process of the ChatterGlove.

ID61. Joanna Timilliotis, Nikolas Oswald, University Hospital Basel, Switzerland.

This study, named Immersive Mental Health with Wearable Biofeedback and VR: Virtual Base, combines the use of two research infrastructures, namely the THOMAS MORE Motion lab – Mobilab & Care and the THOMAS MORE Experience lab (which is described in D9.1).

Virtual Basel is an immersive mental health project that utilizes virtual reality and wearable biofeedback to provide a calming and therapeutic experience for patients. The project includes 360-degree videos of scenic locations in Basel, which are viewed through VR glasses and accompanied by nature sounds, meditations, or classical music. Wearable devices are used to measure the patient's vital signs and provide biofeedback on the VR glasses, allowing them to actively engage in their relaxation and stress- and pain reduction.

During the Transnational Access (TA), several activities are carried out, including the development of a prototype that combines Virtual Reality (VR), Wearables and Biofeedback technologies. The prototype is tested for the first time, and its effectiveness will be evaluated. The concept of the prototype will be refined based on the results of the initial testing, and proof-of-concept tests are conducted to further validate its potential. The insights gained from these activities can help inform future research and development efforts in this field.

The following tools will be required:

- 360° camera (e.g. Insta360° Pro 2)
- VR headset(s) (e.g. Pico Neo 3)
- wearables for monitoring vital signs (Empatica watch)

Data collection:

- Physiological responses to stress and pain through wearables: heart rate, respiratory rate, and skin conductance
- Patient-reported outcome measures: validated measures of pain, disability, quality of life, and patient satisfaction
- Qualitative data concerning patient experience and perceptions of the intervention obtained through semi-structured interviews

3.5 UPM-LifeSTech- The Smart House Living Lab

Here we include a table that presents the current status of each upcoming TA project in UPM-LifeSTech- The Smart House Living Lab.

Table 4 Current status of each upcoming TA project in UPM-LifeSTech- The Smart House Living Lab

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID93	Oct 2023	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No but virtual exchanges

ID93 Paweł Grajkowski, Ewelina Moszyk, Wojciech Witczak, Aleksander Lasecki

This project is named PSNC Future Labs. Wait Safe is a patient queue management system used in clinics and hospitals. The aim of the project is to reduce the risk of infection caused by the presence of many people in one room, as well as to improve the well-being of patients and medical staff. Through a web service and screens in waiting rooms, patients and medical personnel have access to the queue progress view. Additionally, the patient can register their phone number and receive a notification about their approaching appointment. Thanks to this solution, patients can leave the waiting room and wait in a location of their choice, such as a park or cafe, while monitoring their place in the queue using their mobile device. The use of physical RFID cards also makes the system user-friendly for technologically excluded individuals. Sound notifications are also provided in the waiting room to better adapt the system for people with visual impairments. The Wait Safe system also takes care of the well-being of the doctor. An additional functionality is calling patients to the office. With our card readers, the doctor decides when to call the next patient, allowing them to calmly complete medical documentation after the appointment and meet their physiological needs. The medical unit can also collect statistical data resulting from delays and visit length, allowing for better optimization of patient scheduling in individual rooms.

4 Conclusion

This document presents an overview about the performed and upcoming TA activities to four research infrastructures that participate in this work package, highlighting the significance of transnational access in facilitating collaborative research efforts across different research infrastructures. By granting researchers access to state-of-the-art Living Lab infrastructures, the project aims to foster innovation, advance knowledge in the field of transitional care and highlight its critical role.

As the first interim report, this document offers a snapshot of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP9's TA2. It signifies the project's progress towards fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of transitional care. This report serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, providing insights into the project's TA outcomes and setting the stage for the comprehensive final report due in month 36 (March 2024).

5 Annexes

5.1 Annex 1 – Report on TA ID9

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

Report for Transnational Access

(Version 1.0, Jan 2023)

Introduction

This is the **Report for Transnational Access (TA)** to be used for reporting the activities you have performed during your TA in one of the VITALISE Living Lab. Please remember that it is mandatory to fill in this report entirely with the required information in order to receive the refund for the expenses covered for your TA.

For teams only

Specify the roles of each person of the teams during TA.

Name and Surname	Role
1 Fatjona Kamberi	Participation in fast-track training A co-creation session with chronic patients
2 Jerina Jaho	Participation in fast-track training A co-creation session with healthcare professionals
3 Glodiana Sinanaj	Participation in fast-track training Facilitator-Reporter of the co-creation session with the chronic patients
4 Brunilda Subashi	Participation in fast-track training Facilitator-Reporter of the co-creation session with the chronic patients
5	

1. Describe the activities that you conducted (up to 1 page)

Before our visit, we spent one day of virtual access (through virtual meeting), where the LL personnel supported us in the planning of our research study and the definition our research objectives. During our visit to the AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab, , we had the opportunity to participate in the fast-track training activities. These activities included the introduction of AUTH (Lab of Medical Physics & Digital Innovation, School of Medicine), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, and a visit to the AUTH infrastructures. Presentation of the NOTE-the-book-making platform for studying, participation in capacity building, and training sessions such as the Ethical Framework in AUTH Transnational Access, a short intro into Living Labs (LL) and LL services, Vitalise and the importance of harmonization, LL methodologies, persona templates, a methodology workshop, panel management methodologies and tools, Experimentation and co-creation in the Thessahall Living Lab and Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness, and Sustainability approaches. During the fast-track training, we had the opportunity for active discussion and to ask questions. The fast-track training was followed by the co-creation sessions that were related to our study objectives. After the Fast Track Training program, during the third day of our visit, we discussed how and where we will conduct the co-creation session with healthcare professionals, the consultation of the guided list of questions, the ethical framework, the data management, and in what language this session would be conducted. After active discussions, we decided to conduct the co-creation session with healthcare professionals in the settings of the “*Hippokration*” General Hospital of Thessaloniki in English. Before conducting the co-creation session, each participant gave written informed consent. This session with the healthcare professionals was composed of seven participants, including specialists in cardiology, surgery, psychology, and general medicine. The second phase included a co-creation session with older adults. For that, we decided to use a combination of validated standard questionnaires and a list with guiding questions in relation to chronic care and quality of life. Given

the age of the participants, we decided to conduct the co-creation session in Greek. For this co-creation, we used the following tools: L.A.D.L. (The Lawton, Instrumental Activities of Daily Living) scale; Health Questionnaire (EQ-5D-5L); and McGill Questionnaire Quality of Life. The focus group was conducted in the settings of the ThessAHALL and was composed of 10 participants, between 65-90 years of age. Before the co-creation session, each participant provided written informed consent. During the last day of the visit, we discussed with the AUTH LL personel about the analysis strategy and next steps for common publication.

6 Check the services you used during your TA

Please check all the services you used during the TA.

SERVICES	USED
Networking and Capacity building	
Capacity building	x
Equipment and facility rental service	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	x
Grant writing and funding application support service	
Temporary research funding	
Innovation network orchestration	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Marketing and sales support	
Panel management	x
Public procurement support services	
Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	
Project planning and management	
Intake and matching	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	x
Temporary research funding	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Living lab project planning and management	x
Panel management	x
Market and competitor intelligence services	
Access to data	
Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	
Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	

SERVICES	USED
Co-creation	
Co-creation session	x
Expert opinion, and advisory services	x
Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	x
Public procurement support services	
Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	x
Testing and Validation	
Clinical trials	
Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Idea selection and testing	x
Impact assessment and validation test	
Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	
Prototyping test	
Simulation test	
Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	x
Usability testing	
Advisory services	
Public procurement support services	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	x
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Marketing and sales support	
Expert opinion, and advisory services	
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	
Marketing and sales support	
Public procurement support services	
Other services (please indicate which)	
...	

7 Describe how you use these services, technologies and tools to carry out your research project (0,5 page)

The services, tools, and methodologies helped us set-up the co-creation sessions. We held a co-creation session with older adults and a second one with healthcare professionals. For the co-creation sessions, we used the legal, regulatory, and safety standard support in relation to the ethical regulations, and all the ethical rules were applied independently during the conduction of the focus groups by the focus group population. Also, based on the study objective, we used the tool of creating a persona that represents the best characteristics of our study population. The focus groups were conducted in the AUTH ThessAHALL and in the settings of the “*Hippokration*” General Hospital of Thessaloniki. Networking and capacity-building activities helped us analyze and map the stakeholders relevant to our project. For the data collection, we used validated tools translated into Greek for the co-creation session with the older adults and a list of guiding questions in English for the co-creation session with the healthcare professionals.

8 Describe the results achieved (0, 5 page)

Seven people made up the co-creation session with the healthcare professionals, including experts in general medicine, surgery, psychology, and cardiology. Their ages ranged from 20 to 45, and they had 2 to 25 years of clinical practice amongst them. Three participants held doctoral degrees, three bachelor's degrees, and one master's degree. A semi-structured interview guide was used, including open questions, introductory questions, transition questions, and key questions. Some of the questions of the interview focused on these issues: difficulties in discharge and transfer processes for older patients with complex care needs; patients' perceptions of discharge and transfer; resources required for optimal transfers; and how these difficulties were alleviated. The participants disclosed that a lack of communication among key healthcare actors made it difficult for them to discharge and transfer older persons with complicated needs. According to the focus group members, an assigned manager for this activity is one of the resources needed for optimal healthcare transitions. Heart failure, stroke, and neurological disorders were the most often mentioned chronic care diseases requiring transitional care. The severity of the problem was one of the most often mentioned grounds for moving patients from the hospital to transitional care. The patients' perceptions of discharge and transitions were primarily attributed to their knowledge of the recommended treatment regimens. The second co-creation session was conducted in the settings of the AUTH ThessAHALL and was composed of 10 participants, ranging in age from 65 to 90. In the Lawton Instrumental Activities of Daily Living scale, almost all the participants responded that they can operate a telephone on their own initiative, take care of all shopping needs independently, are responsible for taking medicine at the correct times and dosages, and manage day-to-day purchases but need help with banking and major purchases. The Health Questionnaire (EQ-5D-5L), which rates how good or bad the health is on a specific day, revealed a mean of 80 for the health status. According to the EQ-5D-5L, a score of 100 indicates excellent health, while a score of 0 indicates poor health. All the older adults in the focus group expressed no problems in walking, were able to take care of themselves, had no problems doing the usual activities, had no pain or discomfort, and some of them expressed being slightly anxious or depressed. For the McGill Questionnaire Quality of Life, the participants expressed a mean score of 8.5 for the first question in relation to the quality of life in the past two days, where 0 is very bad and 10 is excellent. The question in relation to the thoughts for the future was rated 2.1 by participants, and 8.7 for the meaningful of their lives in the past two days. The rating score for the purpose of the whole life from the participants was 8.2. The participants in the co-creation session in general expressed a good quality of life in the past two days.

A qualitative analysis of both the co-creation sessions is planned to take place, based on the participants answers and remarks. For this purpose, the AUTH personnel will carry out a transcription of the two co-creation sessions, as well as a translation of the co-creation session with the older adults, which was conducted in Greek language.

9 How do you plan to disseminate the results of your research? (0,5 page)

For the dissemination of the results, we intend to publish a research article, a workshop at the institutional level in relation to our visit to the AUTH Living Lab infrastructure, and a report published on the university website. To maximize the impact, we will conduct the same focus groups in Albania, which will allow us to create and publish joint research.

10 Will you allow open access of the collected data? (Y/N)

Yes.

11 Do you intend to commercialise the research results?

Within VITALISE we would like to depict the commercialization potential of the Transnational Access activities. It is mandatory to complete both surveys:

- https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/VITALISE_IR_TAs_VAs
- [KTH Tool](#)

(Please download the second survey (excel file), save it locally and send it along with your report with a file name "KTH_VITALISE_TA_[NAME_SURNAME]")